

THROWING WASTE FROM A CAR IS AS SIGN OF UNCULTURE (PUBLIC OPINION)

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***Abstract.** The research was carried out in the form of a questionnaire, for five days, using the "Telegram" messenger. According to the results of the survey, 589 people read the questionnaires, but more than 191 people (32 %) actively answered the questions. 68 % (398 people) read the questions but did not be an active.*

***Key words:** Pollution of environment, household waste, soil pollution, automobile, ecological culture.*

1. Introduction

As a result of the development of techniques and technology, people of today are given to the mood of laziness and indulgence [1, 2]. The desire to dominate nature makes human society more and more selfish, and the cases of disregarding the laws of nature are increasing. The main and largest source of with the participation of the human factor, and this factor is increasing [3]. Lack of ecological culture and ecological knowledge among people is one of the main reasons for environmental pollution. The cases of daily household waste emitted by humans, including throwing them from the window of a moving car or from the windows of high-rise buildings, indicate that environmental knowledge is very poor [4,5]. Below, the opinion of the population on throwing household waste out of the car window is determined and explained in a sampled in a simple experiment.

2. Method

The research was conducted in the form of a questionnaire. "Telegram" messenger was used for this purpose. The research was conducted anonymously for one week, consisting of 5 questions, two or three different answers, and 589 people got acquainted with the electronic questionnaire directly, of which 32 % (191 people)

answered the questions. 68 % (398 people) of those who read the questionnaire did not answer the questionnaire questions.

Figure 1. Inactive (68 %) and active (32 %)

3. Results

Answers to survey questions were also put into diagrams and analyzed. 191 people answered the first question and the results were represented by the following diagram (Figure 2). Question is that, «Do you throw waste from cars and other vehicles? ».

Figure 2.

The second question of the survey, that is, "Are there many people around doing this?" 184 people answered the question and the answers can be found in the diagram below (Figure 3).

Figure 3.

The third question of the survey, that is, "Is littering from transport common among young people?" 191 people answered the question and the results of the analysis are represented by diagram (Figure 4).

Figure 4.

The fourth question of the anonymous survey, that is, "How does this affect you and your psychology?" and 190 people answered the question, and these answers are represented by diagram (Figure 5).

Figure 5.

The fifth question of the anonymous survey, "Do you think that have a legal punishment for people who throws waste from the car?" and 198 people answered the question, and the results are illustrated by diagram (Figure 6).

Figure 6.

4. Discussion

As it can be seen above, it was found out that most of the participants in the questionnaire (73 %) do not have the habit of throwing waste from the car. 14 % of respondents answered «Yes», and 13 % answered «Sometimes». Analyzing the answers based on the second question of the questionnaire, 45 % of the participants expressed the opinion that there are many people who do the same around them, 24 % of the participants said that there are not many, and 31 % of the participants answered that they sometimes do the same. Most of the participants (68 %) expressed the opinion that young people are more likely to throw waste from cars than adults. A small number of participants (11 %) expressed that they did not have such an opinion, and 21 % said that they even did not know about it. A very large

number of participants (75 %) said that they get angry when household waste is thrown from vehicles, 7 % of people do not get angry with it, and 18 % of participants said that it does not matter for them. 47 % of the participants think that there is a fine for throwing household waste through vehicles, while 36 % think that it is not. 17 % of people say that they are not aware of it.

5. Conclusion

Although the majority of the population does not throw household waste from the windows of cars, it is very sad that 14 % of people do this, and 13 % of people do this sometimes. Sometimes 13 % of people who do such work are also considered polluters of the environment. So, 13 % and 14 %, and at the result is 27 % and it is also big indicator. The opinion of the majority of the society (45 %) is as follows: «There are many people who throw waste from cars». Most of the participants are of the opinion that representatives of the younger generation damage the environment more than adults. Most of the participants stated that they are angry about the situation of throwing waste from the vehicle, which indicates that many people are not indifferent to nature. On the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, there is a fine for throwing household waste from vehicles, including moving cars.

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